

ISic3532

Fragment of an epitaph

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

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Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Necropolis at the Orti della Maddalena

Coordinates

38.183881, 15.549950

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale
interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory A3581

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 19.5 cm

Width 19 cm

Depth not measured cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1-7: 10-20 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]
2. [---]ορίων
3. [---]νίσσα ζών
4. [τεξέπο]ίησαν έα
5. [υτοϊςκαί] μητήρι ν
6. [---ένθά]δε Νείκη
7. [---]καί ηγυ
8. [---]ηρκη

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493863
EDCS 38200017
PHI 313656

Bibliography

Bitto, I. 2001. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Messina. *Pelorias* 7. Messina. At 25

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